

Please indicate how much you **agree** or **disagree** with the following statements.
You can also add comments for each statement, if you feel you need to clarify your answer.

SD: Strongly Disagree

D: Disagree

N: Neutral

A: Agree

SA: Strongly Agree

I am satisfied with the discussion

Comments:

SD	D	N	A	SA

The discussion helped me understand similarity and contrast in music

Comments:

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The group work helped me understand how structure in music can be achieved through similarity and contrast

Comments:

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The final result is a nice piece of music

Comments:

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The final result makes a good use of similarity and contrast

Comments:

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The final result is original

Comments:

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I enjoyed discussing music with a group of people

Comments:

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SD D N A SA

The tabletop interface was a good medium for the explanation and discussion of musical ideas

Comments:

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I felt in control during the discussion

Comments:

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I felt in control during the composition task

Comments:

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I felt that I was able to undertake the final composition challenge

Comments:

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I felt that I could contribute to the collaboration

Comments:

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I felt comfortable contributing to the collaboration

Comments:

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I felt that I was contributing a lot to the group work

Comments:

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I felt that my contributions were appreciated by the group

Comments:

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SD D N A SA

I feel that the final piece of music reflects the way in which the group worked

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Comments:

I felt it was easy to communicate my ideas and intentions to the group

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Comments:

I felt it was easy to discuss ideas and intentions with the group

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Comments:

The interface was frustrating

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Comments:

The interface was confusing

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Comments:

The interface supported the discussion and group work

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Comments:

The interface gave me clear feedback on what was happening at all times

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Comments:

The interface made it easy to communicate my ideas and intentions to the group

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Comments:

SD D N A SA

The interface made it easy to discuss ideas and intentions with the group

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Comments:

I am confident in my ability to compose original music

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Comments:

I will compose original music in the future

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Comments:

Any other comments?

If you participated in the previous individual session, which did you prefer?

this

previous

Why did you prefer it?